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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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**ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF *Plectranthus amboinicus*
(KAPPARAWALLIYA) PLANT AQUEOUS EXTRACTS**

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Abstract: *Plectranthus amboinicus* Lour. (Sinhala Kapparawalliya) is a semi-succulent perennial plant found in the tropical regions of Africa, Asia, and Australia. Since ancient times, this plant has been widely used in Ayurvedic medicine, with over 50 recipes in the Ayurvedic pharmacopeia featuring it as a major ingredient. Studies conducted to date have identified several phytoconstituents, including phenolics, terpenoids, phenolic acids, flavonoids, flavones, and tannins. This present study was conducted to evaluate the *in vitro* antioxidant activity of *Plectranthus amboinicus* plant extracts using two distinct assays: 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging and Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP). Healthy *P. amboinicus* Lour plants were collected from Kuliyaipitiya in the Kurunegala district. The collected plants were washed, dried, ground, and subjected to aqueous extraction by simple maceration. The antioxidant activity was assessed using the DPPH and FRAP assays for a concentration series ranging from 20 µg/mL to 120 µg/mL, and triplicated. Results of the DPPH radical scavenging assay revealed that the half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of *P. amboinicus* plant extract was 83.88 ± 0.18 µg/mL. This result was compared to the positive control, ascorbic acid (IC₅₀ 6.31 ± 0.11 µg/mL). In the FRAP assay, *P. amboinicus* plant extract exhibited an IC₅₀ of 125.31 ± 0.46 µg/mL, while the ascorbic acid positive control exhibited an IC₅₀ of 7.72 ± 0.16 µg/mL. In conclusion, the *P. amboinicus* plant extract demonstrated strong *in vitro* antioxidant activities in DPPH and FRAP assays. These findings justify the traditional medicinal uses of *P. amboinicus* and highlight its potential as a valuable natural source of antioxidants for various health applications.

Keywords: Antioxidant; DPPH; FRAP; IC₅₀; *Plectranthus amboinicus*

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